

ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE, LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR OF PRINCIPALS AND TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE

MONETTE G. AMORES

monette.amores@deped.gov.ph

0000-0002-7278-6474

Lusacan Elementary School, Tiaong, Quezon, Philippines

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study attempted to find out the relationship of school's organizational culture and principal's leadership behavior to teacher's job performance in the District of Tiaong. The respondents of the study were one hundred (100) elementary school teachers in the District of Tiaong, Division of Quezon. Survey questionnaire was the main instrument in gathering the data. Findings of study include the following: Organizational culture of school in terms of involvement, consistency, and adaptability are much evident, while mission is fairly evident. Principal's leadership behavior in terms of direct supervision of instruction and accountable management is fairly evident but much evident in bureaucratic management. Teachers' job performance in terms of teaching skills, management skills, discipline and regularity, and interpersonal relations is much practiced. Not all variables of organizational culture of school and leadership behavior of principal have significant relationship to teacher's job performance. Based on the above findings, the following conclusions are drawn: The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between school's organizational culture and teacher's job performance is therefore not accepted. On the other hand, the hypothesis stating leadership behavior of school principal is not significantly related to teacher's job performance is therefore not accepted. In the light of the foregoing findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are endorsed: It is suggested to study whether organizational culture and principal's leadership behavior has relationship with students' performance. It may also be recommended to create study about school's readiness and principal's competencies which may adapt to drastic change of school system and to implement new modes of learning. A follow-up study parallel to this study maybe conducted with the inclusion of other variables like stakeholder participation in terms of parental and community involvement.

Keywords: School Organizational Culture, Leadership Behavior, Job Performance.